

Video Streaming QoE Meets Programmable Data Planes: The Case of In-Network QoE for 360° VR

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ABSTRACT

Recent advancements in video streaming technologies have brought about a new era of user experiences, including gaming and online events. However, ensuring a good user experience remains a significant challenge. The pursuit of self-driving networks has increased the demand for intelligent, edge-based networking solutions. Delivering high-quality video streaming experiences faces hurdles such as varying network conditions, device diversity, and content complexity, along with the inter-twinned adaptivity of over-the-top services and modern network management systems. In this work, we elaborate on video streaming quality of experience (QoE) improvements based on recent advances in programmable networks. We explore the concept of in-network QoE (INQoE) by discussing benefits, challenges, and opportunities. Furthermore, we present a pure data plane strategy to estimate and improve the QoE of 360-degree virtual reality video streaming. Our results show an INQoE management strategy can effectively keep the QoE close to optimal (4.8 on a scale of 5) under a congestion scenario. Finally, we conclude with a roadmap of research challenges and opportunities around INQoE.

INTRODUCTION

The advent of sixth-generation (6G) mobile networks is underway with a focus on offering intelligent, edge-based networking services tailored to support evolving applications [1], [2] characterized by stringent service-level objectives, particularly within the realm of multimedia/entertainment. For instance, applications like immersive virtual experiences, interactive metaverse environments, and drone-generated content exemplify this trend [3]. One of the primary hurdles in establishing the viability of such applications lies in guaranteeing a favorable quality of experience (QoE) for the end user. This task becomes especially complex given the stringent performance requirements that these applications demand, such as minimal latency and large bandwidth.

Exemplifying this, recent work [4] has shown that an increase of 5 ms in latency can degrade QoE from 8 to 36 percent in virtual reality (VR) video streaming applications.

To meet the demands of these applications and deliver a satisfying QoE for users, the network should make timely decisions and adjust network policies in response to the root causes of QoE degradation. To this end, it is fundamental to rely on efficient monitoring capabilities. Recent research efforts [5], [6] have focused on monitoring user QoE and applying different network policies to improve it if necessary. However, despite their accuracy in estimating and predicting user QoE, strategies based on QoE inference in the user's player or control plane are often insufficient for the next generation of video streaming applications. To change some network policy, for example, in the event of a problem, these strategies need to communicate with the data plane, taking around up to tens of milliseconds [7], which is beyond the latency requirements of some applications [1].

With the recent advent of network programmability, efforts have been devoted to moving QoE inference and optimization from the control plane to the data plane [8], [9]. For instance, [8] have shown that QoE video streaming can be inferred by analyzing in-network data plane metrics such as inter-packet gap (IPG).

Enhancing QoE directly within the network infrastructure, hereafter referred to as **in-network QoE (INQoE)**, translates into reduced latency, more efficient resource utilization, and improved user QoE. An INQoE approach can provide faster content delivery and real-time adaptation to changing network conditions. Furthermore, INQoE optimization can contribute to lower operational costs by detecting network issues and service quality problems early, addressing potential hazards before they escalate.

Despite the benefits of INQoE optimization techniques, its deployment requires substantial efforts to ensure effectiveness, reliability, and accuracy. Challenges inherent to in-network computing fundamentally encompass constraints related to the limited computational capabilities of existing

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programmable network devices.¹ These constraints include implementation limitations, such as programmable switch support for floating point operations, loops, and complex comparisons, or performance degradation, such as achieving throughput levels below the supported capacity, affecting the accuracy and performance of the solutions [7].

In this work, we revolve around the concept of INQoE management by deliberating about the benefits, challenges, and drawbacks of QoE monitoring and improvement techniques unlocked by programmable networks. Previous studies illuminate the landscape of INQoE monitoring. While [8] estimates QoE in the data plane and relies on the control plane for decision-making, [9] can optimize QoE in the data plane but depends directly on the control plane to apply QoE improvement policies. We focus on the first strategy able to estimate and improve the QoE entirely in the data plane. Furthermore, based on our experience, we identify the current research challenges and future directions to research. The main contributions of this article can be synthesized as follows:

- Discussion of the concept of INQoE management and its realization challenges;
- Assay of the first full data plane strategy that not only estimates but also improves QoE of 360° VR streaming;
- Overview of research opportunities around INQoE towards self-driven network infrastructures.

RELATED WORK

In the contemporary digital landscape, the estimation and enhancement of QoE have emerged as pivotal instruments for network management and optimization. In [4], an objective QoE model is defined to estimate the QoE of video sessions and uses a combination of the metrics video quality, video stalls, quality/resolution switches, and startup time. The model is developed to infer the QoE of 360-degree adaptive tile-based VR video streaming. Understanding the perceptual facets of how network performance directly impacts users' QoE and, by extension, their engagement with digital services.

Recent efforts aimed to deliver network-based intelligence for managing and orchestrating end-user QoE. We can divide existing INQoE measurement approaches into (i) optimization [5], [9], and (ii) estimation methods [4], [12], [13], [14]. Iurian et al. [9] proposes a method to optimize QoE with priority queues. However, the method

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does not perform QoE inference nor provides an implementation in programmable hardware. Similarly, Vidhya et al. [5] leverages network data and application function 5G entity metrics, such as video rate and freezing, to optimize QoE by continuously feeding the policy control function.

The efforts above mostly rely on predicting the user experience based on the control plane and end-user metrics. On the other hand, Bronzino et al. [14] infer quality metrics for encrypted streaming video services from a mix of traffic, where the time precision of the collected statistics is coarse due to aggregation. Similarly, Filho et al. [4] proposed a two-stage machine learning (ML)-assisted approach to infer how users perceive the streamed VR video's performance at the user plane. Despite their effectiveness, the previous strategies still depend on the control plane to make decisions and apply new policies, which increases their response time to problems. In contrast, Table 1 presents the performance requirements (network latency and bandwidth) for today's video streaming applications (e.g., supported by current mobile networks) and future video streaming applications. These requirements are state-of-the-art estimates based on the characteristics of each application. The exact value for these requirements will depend on characteristics other than those presented in the table, such as data compression. These requirements highlight the need for methods capable of responding more quickly to problems, and with this in mind, QoEyes [8] took the first step towards performing QoE estimation entirely in the data plane. However, no (data- or control-plane) actions are taken after QoE degradation is inferred.

In this article, we build upon [8] and expand the strategy to allow queue management decisions to be made directly in the data plane for flows that exhibit poor QoE estimations.

INQoE: IN-NETWORK QoE MANAGEMENT

The advent of programmable network devices through languages like programming protocol-independent packet processors (P4) paves the way for migrating numerous network monitoring and management strategies, traditionally executed in the control plane, to be offloaded to the data plane [15]. Novel strategies can

Use case	Latency	Bandwidth	Technology	Single-eye resolution	Full resolution	Frame rate
Previous VR [10], [11]	10-40 ms	25-35 Mb/s	4G	1 K×1 K	4 K	30-60
4K/8K HD [1]	15-35 ms	35-140 Mb/s	5G/6G	-	4K/8K	30-60
Entry VR [10], [11]	10-30 ms	100-210 Mb/s	5G	2 K×2 K	8 K	30-90
Advanced VR [10], [11]	5-20 ms	410-796 Mb/s	5G	4 K×4 K	12 K	60-120
Ultimate VR [10], [11]	5-10 ms	4.42-6.37 GB/s	6G	8 K×8 K	24 K	60-200
XR [1]	5-7 ms	25 Mb/s-5 Gb/s	5G/6G	2 K×2 K	8 K	60
Holographic [1]	<1 ms	4-10 Tb/s	6G	-	-	-

TABLE 1. Literature-based estimated bandwidth and network latency of video streaming applications.

¹ P416 Intel Tofino Native Architecture-Public Version. Available at: <https://github.com/barefootnetworks/Open-Tofino>.

leverage advantages such as real-time monitoring and enhanced data granularity, rendering them exceptionally efficient in network monitoring and management – particularly appealing for latency-sensitive applications. Next, we discuss how video streaming applications can utilize these advantages through INQoE monitoring.

PROBLEM OVERVIEW

Figure 1 presents an overview of a programmable network infrastructure with INQoE monitoring. We can see there are users of different types of video streaming applications and servers that provide this content. In this network infrastructure, the network devices (e.g., switches) are responsible for monitoring and improving the QoE of the active video sessions without the need for interference from the network control plane. In this case, the control plane only receives periodic reports to inform them of the policies being applied but does not need to participate in monitoring and decision-making.

While some existing strategies excel in precise QoE estimation [4], they frequently encounter challenges in meeting the swift response demands of specific applications. These challenges arise because these strategies are typically integrated into the user’s player or control plane, as seen in monitoring applications. Consequently, there is a delay in implementing critical network policies to improve QoE. In contrast, some applications like extended reality (XR) demand very low latency, not exceeding 7 ms, while VR applications are known to require a similarly stringent delay (e.g., as low as 5ms – see Table 1). However, the communication between the control and data plane to send information or change network policies requires close to tens of milliseconds [7]. Therefore, we argue that network operators must harness the power of QoE enhancement within the network infrastructure to meet strict application requirements.

Performing INQoE estimation and management is exceptionally challenging. To illustrate this, consider a network device with thousands of network flows that may or may not be video streaming flows, and each video stream may be from a different application with different performance requirements (e.g., latency and

bandwidth). Then, we need to estimate QoE only for video stream flows with packet-level information (e.g., throughput, inter-arrival times) due to traffic encryption. Furthermore, depending on the network device, we must deal with implementation limitations (e.g., lack of loops, complex comparisons) and/or performance restrictions (e.g., depending on the code, as packet recirculation, mathematical operations, and memory accesses can significantly degrade performance on some programmable device architectures). Finally, QoE estimates can be used to make decisions and change network policies, mitigating possible performance impacts on other types of network applications.

SOLUTION OVERVIEW

As discussed in the section “*Related Work*” and Table 1, the estimated requirements of current video streaming applications are strict. Based on these requirements, such as a latency of less than 10 ms for existing applications, we advocate that INQoE can help to enhance application performance for the current and the next generation of video streaming applications.

To better explore the INQoE concept, we divided it into two parts: INQoE monitoring and INQoE improvement. INQoE monitoring is only responsible for monitoring/estimating/predicting user QoE, while INQoE improvement refers to strategies for improving user QoE. The combination of the two concepts optimizes QoE entirely on the network, meaning that video traffic monitoring and management are carried out on network devices (e.g., programmable switches and SmartNICs).

Next, we present these two concepts and provide examples of how to apply them. In sequence, we present the benefits and drawbacks of deploying these techniques while describing our proposal and the challenges and future directions in more detail in the following sections.

1) INQoE Monitoring – Understanding User Experience: INQoE monitoring is a cornerstone for understanding the user experience. It entails the real-time assessment of network performance, service quality, and user QoE, all within the network infrastructure. Advanced monitoring capabilities are indispensable to gauge how users

FIGURE 1. Illustrating a use case of video streaming INQoE enhancement in a programmable network infrastructure.

perceive the network's performance and identify potential issues. A range of metrics to infer INQoE includes latency, packet loss, packet sizes, IPG, jitter, and content delivery times. These metrics are measurable in the data plane and can be calculated using programmable switches or SmartNICs. Advanced techniques like deep packet inspection, ML algorithms, and data analytics are harnessed to refine the accuracy of INQoE monitoring. To illustrate, consider an example where we evaluate real-time video streaming QoE by measuring buffering times and streaming quality with the data processed in-network to provide immediate insights into the viewer's experience.

2) INQoE Improvement — Enhancing User Experience: INQoE improvement is the proactive response to the insights gleaned from QoE monitoring. The primary objective is to elevate user QoE by mitigating QoE degradation and optimizing network performance. To mitigate QoE degradation directly in the data plane, we can use diverse strategies, including intelligent traffic shaping, quality of service (QoS) policy adjustments, packet deflection, request cloning, and dynamic resource allocation. These approaches can be carried out without interference from the control plane, and network resources can be prioritized and allocated to cater to latency-sensitive applications and ensure a consistent, high-quality user experience. Additionally, content delivery optimization, adaptive bitrate streaming, and content caching techniques are employed to streamline content delivery, minimize buffering, and reduce latency. To exemplify, envision an instance employing traffic prioritization policies to increase the video quality in real time, ensuring a seamless experience for the viewer, regardless of network conditions.

BENEFITS

One of the primary advantages of INQoE monitoring and improvement is its potential to significantly enhance user QoE. Next, we present some benefits of performing INQoE monitoring compared to approaches based on the control plane or the user player.

Quicker Response Time. By estimating INQoE, we have access to real-time monitoring of a user flow. This allows us to make decisions very quickly on a nanosecond scale (e.g., leveraging programmable switches), enabling us to act quickly in case of problems or QoE degradation. For example, we can decide to prioritize a set of packets of a flow in the middle of the path, as we know they are late and will degrade the QoE of a user. This policy would enable early problem detection and resolution, mitigating potential future escalations.

Dynamic Resource Allocation. Programmable data planes enable dynamic resource allocation, ensuring network resources are distributed efficiently in response to fluctuating network conditions and traffic demands. By monitoring real-time data and applying policies, operators can allocate resources where they are most needed, thus optimizing network performance and maintaining a high level of QoE for users. This practice also minimizes over-provisioning resource allocation and maximizes resource utilization, leading to cost savings and better network performance.

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Traffic Prioritization and Content Differentiation. Network operators can differentiate between various types of content, such as video streaming applications, based on their QoE requirements. This differentiation allows them to allocate resources optimally and ensure critical applications receive the necessary resources for optimal performance. For example, we can manage the allocation of traffic to priority queues in real time with different performance guarantees, depending on the estimated QoE and the application's needs. This prioritization mechanism allows for a smoother, more responsive user experience and better resource allocation.

DRAWBACKS

While serving as a valuable tool for elevating user QoE and fine-tuning network performance, INQoE enhancement does come with its set of limitations. Next, we delve into some of the drawbacks linked to INQoE estimation.

Accuracy. As the algorithms executed to estimate INQoE need to be simpler and do not have access to application information (e.g., resolution, fps), this naturally impacts their accuracy (e.g., compared to complex ML methods). Depending on the algorithm, application sensitivity, and network conditions, this impact can be significant. This can cause hasty decisions, resulting in inadequate network policies that can interfere with the QoE of other video applications and even the remaining network traffic.

Intrusiveness. INQoE can be intrusive to the network traffic. QoE improvement policies may inadvertently introduce biases, favoring specific applications or users over others. For example, in extreme cases of QoE degradation, network policies may heavily favor video applications and penalize the rest of the network traffic. Therefore, network operators must carefully design and monitor policies to prevent discrimination and ensure fairness in QoE enhancements.

Resource Consumption. Implementing INQoE improvement policies can consume significant resources regarding processing power and memory within network devices. For example, imagine a network device that has to process Tb/s of traffic and, at the same time, monitor and optimize the QoE for video streaming applications. The device and the algorithm must be feasible for processing and storing large data (depending on

INQE		External QoE	
Benefits	Drawbacks	Benefits	Drawbacks
Lower latency (ns)	Potentially intrusive monitoring	Non-intrusive monitoring	Higher latency (tens of ms)
Dynamic resource allocation	Low accuracy, limited resources	High accuracy, scalable resources	Lower information granularity

TABLE 2. In-network QoE estimation versus Out-of-network QoE estimation.

the algorithm). This resource consumption can increase operational costs and necessitate hardware upgrades to maintain the desired QoE.

SUMMARY AND TAKEAWAYS

Table 2 summarizes the main benefits and drawbacks of performing INQoE enhancement against an external QoE entity, such as the control plane or the user player. In the realm of INQoE enhancement, several valuable lessons emerge. First and foremost, while in-network strategies offer the advantage of real-time data proximity, achieving high accuracy can be a challenge. The lesson is the importance of balancing speed and precision, especially in applications with critical QoE measurements. Conversely, the low latency is a distinct advantage of in-network solutions. Their ability to swiftly identify and address issues is paramount in time-sensitive scenarios such as 5G and 6G video streaming applications. This underscores the significance of quick response as a cornerstone of effective QoE improvement for video streaming applications.

USE CASE: INQoE 360-DEGREE VR STREAMING

A first step towards INQoE optimization involves the development of strategies that estimate the current status of the application quality and deal with possible problems to improve the final user QoE. This aspect is critical to increase the quality of the taken decisions and decrease the reaction time. However, estimating the QoE of video streaming applications entirely on the data plane (i.e., network switch and SmartNIC) is challenging. The challenges come from the fact that in the data plane, there is limited access to application information, not containing, for example, media-specific parameters (e.g., video resolution, frame rate) commonly used to estimate user QoE. This implies that to estimate QoE directly at the network device, we must work with packet- and flow-level information, such as packet size, inter-packet arrival times, etc.

In this use case, we demonstrate the estimation and improvement of QoE for 360-degree VR video streaming applications. We use the IPG as a metric for QoE estimation and queue management to improve the QoE when necessary. Next, we start with an overview of the problem,

followed by a discussion of the proposed solution and its results.

PROPOSED APPROACH

To address the aforementioned challenges, we introduce a QoE estimation technique that uses the IPG calculation to complete the QoE estimation and optimization in the data plane. The IPG metric refers to the time interval between the last packets that arrived. Our strategy is driven by recent academic studies that have already utilized IPG as the primary metric for inferring QoE, demonstrating a direct correlation between IPG and QoE [8], [13]. Furthermore, IPG is a metric simple to calculate, which helps us deal with the implementation limitations imposed by programmable switches. We argue that we can get a QoE estimation for VR video sessions directly in the data plane by calculating the IPG using an exponentially weighted moving average (EWMA), similarly to [8]. However, we argue that reporting this information to the control plane is unnecessary, and we can optimize the QoE directly in the data plane.

Then, we classify traffic into flows using the 5-tuple (source/destination IPs, protocol, and source/destination ports), and for each packet from a VR flow, we calculate its IPG weighted (IPGw) by putting higher weighting to older values. Using a low-pass filter in P4, a network controller can manage weighting on runtime. We then use the result of this calculation to decide when to optimize a flow. To do this, we define a threshold (specific for each video application); if the IPGw of the flow is lower than the threshold, we apply queue management policies to place the flow in a priority queue.

EVALUATION

Setup. We implemented our solution in a commercial programmable switch using the network programming language P4. Figure 2 summarizes the experimentation environment and strategy. In the experiment, we have a server to provide 360-degree VR videos and a set of clients to request these videos. Then, we define one of these clients to have its flow monitored by our strategy, using the IPGw of that flow. The other flows and packets will traditionally be routed

FIGURE 2. Experimental environment of 360-degree VR to evaluate INQoE optimization using in-network IPGw QoE estimation and queue management.

without monitoring or optimization. The objective of the experiment is to introduce a problem into the network, specifically network congestion, and verify whether our strategy can autonomously respond upon detecting QoE degradation. Then, we present the impact of using or not using our strategy and the correlation of the QoE estimation metric used (IPGw) with the throughput and final QoE of the video session.

To perform the experiment, we limit the switch ports to 1 Gb/s throughput and start to run the clients, which will start requesting video sessions from the server using the VR-EXP player [4]. The requested video is *Google Spotlight help*,² sent using HTTP/1.1 and a 12x4 tiling scheme performed by the Kvazaar encoder³. Furthermore, each tiling scheme (30 FPS) has three quality representations: 720p with a bitrate of 1.8 Mbps, 1080p with a bitrate of 2.7 Mbps, and 4k with a bitrate of 6 Mbps.

After the videos start, we introduce background traffic of around 1 Gb/s, leading to congestion and resource competition among the flows. We set the IPGw threshold for the monitored video stream at 1 ms and optimize it when its IPGw exceeds this value. This threshold was chosen to meet the specific requirements of this VR application and ensure a good QoE with a 1 ms IPGw.

Results. Figure 3 presents the performance results for the monitored flow and not monitored flows during the congestion scenario. The blue lines represent monitored (and optimized) flows, while the red lines show flows with normal routing. The continuous lines correspond to the IPGw of these flows (left y-axis). The flow monitored and optimized by our strategy maintains a regular IPGw, even in a congestion situation. In contrast, the unmonitored flow has drastic variations. The dotted lines represent the throughput of these flows (right y-axis), and the optimized flow reaches up to 6 Mb/s, while the non-optimized flow does not reach 2 Mb/s. Finally, we

Furthermore, including real QoE evaluations based on subjective methods was also not carried out, and the QoE model used is guaranteed only to the player used.

measure the final QoE of the video sessions using a mean opinion score (MOS) model proposed in [4]. The QoE results are 4.8 and 2.3 (range of 0-5) for the monitored and not-monitored flows, respectively.

The results indicate that our strategy effectively monitors and optimizes video flows, even during congestion. By setting an appropriate IPGw threshold, we can directly implement traffic prioritization policies in the data plane. We may need to determine different thresholds for applications with varying latency and bandwidth requirements and establish “problem tolerance limits” based on each application’s specific needs.

LIMITATIONS AND DISCUSSION

Despite being effective in detecting and responding to QoE degradation in 360-degree VR videos, the proposed method is just an initial step in the realm of INQoE monitoring and improvement. It has inherent limitations and may not apply universally to all situations (e.g., XR/AR application) which can lead to QoE degradation. A more extensive evaluation in other scenarios with higher data rates and fps, other applications, and even real VR glasses could evaluate the generalization capacity of the method to different video streaming scenarios. Furthermore, including real QoE evaluations based on subjective methods was also not carried out, and the QoE model used is guaranteed only to the player used. About our method, one limitation is our exclusive use of IPGw as a QoE estimation metric, which may not encompass all types of issues, for example, in situations involving periodic packet losses or variations in throughput, where the packet frequency remains consistent, and only the packet size changes, IPGw might not promptly or accurately detect these problems.

FIGURE 3. Performance evaluation during a congestion of INQoE monitored versus non-monitored flows of a 360-degree VR application.

² Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G-XZhKqQAHU>.

³ Available at: <https://github.com/ultravideo/kvazaar>.

In such cases, a more effective approach could involve combining IPGw with metrics like packet loss and bitrate, offering a more comprehensive QoE monitoring and enhancement strategy. Moreover, an additional constraint lies in the potential intrusiveness of enhancing QoE through queue management, especially when prioritizing VR traffic upon detecting QoE degradation. This intrusiveness becomes apparent when a substantial number of flows experience low QoE. In such cases, prioritizing multiple VR flows can penalize the remaining network traffic.

We reckon that our threshold-based method is tailored to our specific VR application and may not be equally effective for all video application types. Generalizing it to other video applications requires analyzing each specific application, identifying suitable thresholds, and implementing traffic classification. Considering the limitations in the presented strategy, we can say there is still a long way to go for INQoE estimation and improvement for all applications and problems.

RESEARCH CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS ON INQoE OPTIMIZATION

Despite the benefits, INQoE estimation for different applications is a complex endeavor due to distinct and often stringent requirements of various content types. Video streaming in 4K/8K demands high resolution and bitrate, necessitating substantial bandwidth and low latency to prevent buffering while maintaining high-resolution quality. On the other hand, VR, XR, and holographic applications introduce unique challenges, as they rely on ultra-low latency to ensure real-time immersion and interactivity. These applications demand precise and rapid QoE estimation capabilities to adapt network resources to their specific needs. Furthermore, estimating QoE on the data plane includes a number of other challenges and limitations. Next, we summarize a few of them and provide possible directions:

Programmable Hardware Limitations. Programmable network devices are constrained by limited resources and computational capabilities (e.g., limited arithmetic and logic units). These constraints ensure restricted access to memory. Hence, as packet processing remains within the bounds required for line-rate packet forwarding, some workarounds, like employing fixed-point representations of real numbers and packet recirculation, have been utilized, but these methods can constrain the accuracy of the computing performed in the data plane. Additionally, packet recirculation introduces significant latency, which may be problematic for certain video streaming applications. To mitigate these limitations, one potential approach is to leverage hardware offloading, such as embedding missing functionalities on field-programmable gate arrays or data processing units.

QoE Data Plane Metrics. Programmable data plane can expose many internal networking/device metrics that can be used to enhance video streaming QoE. These metrics can include from intrinsic dataplane metadata (e.g., queue occupancy) to customized ones (e.g., IPG [8] or video-streaming bitrate). Different video streaming monitoring techniques can demand different

networking/application metrics to infer QoE properly. As an example, VR-based video streaming is encoded in a tile-based format, and, therefore, it might demand information regarding different regions of tiles being streamed directly in the data plane (e.g., the bitrate of a specific region of tiles). Currently, many QoE inference models [4] rely on metrics captured at the player side, like the number of stalls, buffering time, and resolution switching (e.g., dynamic adaptive streaming over HTTP (DASH) systems). In this context, capturing player-side metrics by observing the networking itself is challenging. By applying these metrics and designing new ones to improve QoE, there are a plethora of research opportunities ahead — i.e., data plane applications can rely on these QoE metrics to react to networking events to circumvent QoE degradation.

QoE Data Plane Inference. Recent studies have offloaded ML techniques into the data plane [15], including artificial neural networks, clustering, and decision trees. These techniques enable QoE inference to be done directly in the data plane. However, applying such techniques is not trivial for many reasons. First, the effective success of ML strongly depends on the metrics being evaluated. Therefore, a deep understanding of which data plane metrics impact QoE the most is required. Second, applying supervised methods requires substantial training datasets correlating internal data plane metrics, networking conditions, and video streaming characteristics with obtained QoE. Third, unsupervised methods require substantial computing efforts to retrain clusters over time. That is infeasible in the current programmable commodity switch but can be done in emerging SmartNICs. Fourth, using an ML-based data plane leads to the question of where to run such intelligence: would it be in the SmartNIC on the server side? Or in the programmable switch in the core network? Or a hybrid deployed solution?

QoE-Based Data Plane Decisions. To improve the perceived QoE of video streaming or to circumvent networking conditions that might degrade it, the data plane should autonomously apply network policies to specific video streaming network flows. Networking policies might include routing and scheduling decisions directly to networking flows of video streaming of interest. That would allow, for example, the application of routing/scheduling QoE-aware strategies directly in the data plane. However, implementing QoE policies in programmable data planes can be challenging. Creating and maintaining policies that effectively enhance QoE while adapting to evolving network conditions requires in-depth knowledge and expertise. Additionally, the intricacy of these policies can lead to operational challenges and potential misconfiguration.

CLOSING REMARKS

In this work, we introduced the concept of INQoE and discussed the benefits, challenges, and limitations of performing QoE monitoring and enhancements within programmable network infrastructures. Adequate QoE monitoring and improvement methods that overcome the limitations of current in-network computing capabilities are needed to realize the full potential of INQoE through network programmability. We showcase

the first pure data plane autonomous strategy for estimating and effectively improving the QoE of 360° VR video streaming without any control plane intervention. In addition to the advances related to our open-source prototype implementation⁴, we expect that our overview of research challenges and future directions will foster new research contributions in the flourishing field of INQoE/QoS management.

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⁴ Code repository and data sets for reproducible research available at <https://github.com/intrig-unicamp>.